

VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF PAPER FROM SOFTWOOD AND HARDWOOD PULP WITH ADDED CHITOSAN

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Abstract: *Due to the external stress and change in ambient temperature, the viscoelastic properties of the material play an important role in determining the use of the final product. The viscoelasticity varies depending on the intensity of relaxation phenomena and the modes of molecular segment displacements in the material structure. In the case of paper, the viscoelastic properties are strongly determined by the cellulose fibre network, crystallinities of cellulose, different modifications of cellulose and by the heterogeneous nature of its structure. In this study, chitosan was introduced into the softwood and hardwood pulp as an additive together with retention additives. The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of chitosan in two different concentrations (5% and 7.5%), on the viscoelastic properties of the paper. The analytical method such as dynamic mechanical analysis, supported by the tensile test, water absorption capacity, capillary rise and surface properties characterizations were carried out. The results showed that the reduced stiffness of the paper with chitosan was not proportional to the amount of the additive. The stiffness of the paper improved with increasing chitosan concentration (7.5%) but remained lower compared to the paper with retention additive. It was observed that the storage modulus of the paper composites increased with the addition of the retention additive, which could be attributed to the increase in retention additive in correlation with cellulose interactions. Since the dynamic mechanical analysis confirmed that the retention additive*

increased the elastic stiffness of the paper, so it is more reasonable to use it as a reinforcing additive of the paper structure. In contrast, the elasticity of the paper was reduced with added chitosan regardless of its concentration, which is due to the sensitivity of chitosan to ambient moisture. The cellulose matrix was altered by chitosan, which was also confirmed by the moisture properties. As expected, sample with only pulp had the highest moisture content (10%), which decreased with the additives in the paper composition. Chitosan embedded the cellulose fibres and partially filled the pores of the papers, as demonstrated by scanning electron microscope. Therefore, the reduction of sizing and the conferring of hydrophobic character to the surfaces of the coated papers were observed.

Keywords: polysaccharide; additive; material; dynamic mechanical analysis; surface properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interest in biodegradable polymers has been directed also to packaging materials, which were derived from renewable resources. Such polymer is also chitosan, which is already fabricated in many applications (Santos et al., 2020;). The linear macromolecules of cellulose form strong crystallites and weak non crystalline (amorphous) domains by means of hydrogen bonds formed between the side hydrogen atoms of one chain and the hydroxyl groups of the glucose units of the adjacent chain (Li et al., 2015; Lindh et al., 2016). On a structural level, paper can be regarded as a dense network of cellulose fibres, consisting of cellulose microfibrils embedded in a matrix of lignin and hemicellulose. Chitosan acts as an antibacterial agent and as a water barrier affects the water resistance of the paper (Abd El-Hack et al., 2020). It is poorly soluble in water, while it achieves its water resistance by combining its amino groups with the hydroxyl groups of cellulose, thereby forming strong hydrogen bonds that prevent water from binding to the cellulose molecule (Flores-Hernández et al., 2018; Cazón et al., 2020). Paper with added chitosan can be used to produce packaging materials for the storage of a substance requiring protection against microbes and moisture (such as food). Modified cationic polyacrylamide (PAM), which was also used as a retention additive, is a polymer composed of acrylamide units. As an additive in paper, it is widely used to achieve the strength of the bond between cellulose fibers, which provides better paper support. In paper, it also functions as a plasticizer, as it allows other additives to bind to the cellulose fibers. It also absorbs water very well and polymerizes into a linear or branched structure. By changing the

ambient temperature, the viscoelastic properties of the material play an important role in determining the use of the final product. The viscoelasticity depends on the intensity of relaxation phenomena and the modes of molecular segment shifts in the material structure. In the case of paper, the viscoelastic properties are strongly determined by the different modifications and crystallinities of the cellulose and by the heterogeneous structure. The production of improved paper with enhanced tensile properties using biodegradable macromolecules is quite limited. Therefore, the primary objective of this research was to determine the influence of different paper fillers, i.e. retention filler, chitosan, along with two concentrations, on the temperature dependent relaxation transitions as well as the viscoelastic properties of the paper.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The softwood pulp was delivered by SCA (Sweden) and is bleached sulphate kraft cellulose from pine and spruce trees. The hardwood pulp was delivered by Svilosa AD (Bulgaria) and is bleached hardwood kraft pulp from beech trees. The kraft pulp is placed on the market under the registered trade mark SVILOCELL[®]. Chitosan, with the molecular weight lower than 20 kDa and deacetylation degree higher than 85%, was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Austria). Acetic acid (99%) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Austria). Modified cationic polyacrylamide was delivered by Kemira (Finland) and is with molecular weight of $11 \cdot 10^6$ g/mol, charge density of 1,05 meq/g, viscosity (Brookfield) 700 cP_(0,5%,25°C) and conductivity 66,6 μ S_(0,5%).

2.2 Methods

Preparation of the pulp

In our research two types of kraft pulp – softwood and hardwood were used. They were refined by laboratory Jokro mill method with six refining units, according to the standard ISO 5264-3:21979. The refining concentration in each unit was 6% (16g o.d.f in 267ml water). The two celluloses were refined separately.

Preparation of pulp suspensions and preparation of paper sheets

Four combinations of paper suspensions were prepared by using chitosan (Fluka, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) and retention additive polyacrylamide (Merck, Germany). The raw material consisted 50% of softwood (pine and spruce) and 50% of hardwood (beech) cellulose pulp. Both, 5% and 7.5% chitosan solutions

were prepared by dissolving chitosan in acetic acid at 85 °C at 10min mixing and then cooled to room temperature. Paper suspensions were obtained as follows: 23.5g o.d.f. cellulose pulp were stirred in tap water (2000 ml), then the chitosan were added and mixed followed by the retention additive. All paper samples were prepared on paper laboratory machine (Rapid-Kothen, Germany) acc. ISO 5269-2:2005, with a grammage of 80g/m², with drying conditions of 96 °C and duration of 7 minutes. The obtained paper suspensions were as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Paper sheets with included additives

Sample	Paper additives and componets
<i>P</i>	<i>Only pulp</i>
<i>PR</i>	<i>Pulp and 0.05% retention additive</i>
<i>5% CH</i>	<i>Pulp, 5% chitosan, 0.05% retention additive</i>
<i>7.5% CH</i>	<i>Pulp, 7.5% chitosan, 0.05% retention additive</i>

Grammage, density, specific surface, thickness

Grammage of all paper samples was determined in accordance with the ISO 536 standard. Density and specific surface volume were calculated form grammage and thickness, as described in the standard method ISO 534 (Table 2).

Table 2: Basic properties (grammage, thickness, specific surface and density) of all paper samples.

Properties	Samples			
	<i>P</i>	<i>PR</i>	<i>5% CH</i>	<i>7.5% CH</i>
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>80</i>	<i>80</i>
<i>Thickness (mm)</i>	<i>0.085</i>	<i>0.094</i>	<i>0.092</i>	<i>0.094</i>
<i>Specific surface (m³/g)</i>	<i>0.0012</i>	<i>0.0012</i>	<i>0.0012</i>	<i>0.0013</i>
<i>Density (g/m³)</i>	<i>952.40</i>	<i>842.12</i>	<i>879.13</i>	<i>842.12</i>

Dynamic mechanical analysis

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed on a TA instrument (DMA Q800, TA Instruments, USA) with a controlled gas-cooling accessory.

Samples with chitosan (regardless of its concetrantion), similar to the paper with retention filler (sample PR), also showed two temperature relaxation area with the increased transition temperatures. These were: 20.07 °C and 22.21 °C at 5% and 7.5% of added chitosan, respectively in first relaxation transition and 171.30 °C and 179.15 °C at 5% and 7.5% of added chitosan, in the second relaxation area, respectively (Fig.1 (a-c)).

Figure 1: Dynamic mechanical properties of paper with added chitosan a) storage modulus (E'), b) loss modulus (E'') and c) tangens delta ($T_g \delta$) versus temperature at 10 Hz of oscillation

Tensile test

Tensile strength (TS) and elongation at break (E) of papers were determined on a tensile testing machine Instron 6022 (Instron, USA) at standard atmosphere at 23 °C and 50% of relative humidity.

Paper with blends of fillers achieved higher tensile strength but lower elongations, compare to paper sheets where only chitosan was added (Table 3). The positively charged chitosan was introduced between negatively charged cellulose fibres, therefore the decrease in Young's modulus has also been detected.

Table 3: Tensile properties of paper samples

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
P	54.05	2.41
PR	54.70	2.36
5% CH	57.80	2.38
7.5% CH	59.32	2.30

Moisture content, water absorptivness (Cobb value) and capillary rise (Klemm method)

Five samples of each paper were tested for moisture content in accordance with ISO 287. Water absorption capacity (the Cobb₆₀ value, g/m²) was determined as described in the standard method ISO 535 and capillary rise was determined as described in ISO 8787.

From Table 4, the sample with only pulp (sample P) had the highest moisture content (10.2 %), which decreased with the additives in the paper composition. The same trend was observed in water absorptivness and capillary rise. Sample P exhibited the most hydrophilic character due to open pores and voids, which was also confirmed by the analysis of SEM (Figure 2). As previously observed, chitosan embedded the cellulose fibres and partially filled the pores of the papers, especially for samples with 5 and 7.5% chitosan. Therefore, a reduction in sizing and a hydrophobic nature of the surfaces of the coated papers were observed.

Table 4: Moisture content, water absorptivness (Cobb value) and capillary rise (Klemm) of analysed samples

Sample	Moisture content (%)	Cobb₆₀ value (g/m²)	Capillary rise (mm)
<i>P</i>	10.2	30.10	46
<i>PR</i>	9.8	28.91	39
<i>5% CH</i>	7.1	27.71	16
<i>7.5% CH</i>	6.9	20.35	11

Scanning electron microscope analysis (SEM)

The SEM micrographs of paper surfaces were taken with a scanning electron microscope (JSM-6060 LV, Japan) and the instrument was operated at 10 kV accelartion andat 500x magnification.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of paper samples, at 500x magnification: a) Sample P, b) Sample PR, c) Sample 5% CH, d) Sample 7.5% CH

3 CONCLUSION

Regarding the elasticity of the paper, the dynamic mechanical analysis confirmed that the retention filler increased the elastic stiffness of the paper, so it is more reasonable to use it as a reinforcing additive of the paper structure. The retention additive increased the elasticity and significantly decreased the relaxation transition temperature of the paper, so the range between 0 °C and 50 °C is not suitable for major mechanical deformation of the paper. Chitosan increased the relaxation transition temperature and decreased the elasticity of the paper with retention additive. Reduction of sizing and increase of hydrophobicity of coated papers were demonstrated.

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